

Preregistration – Initial Negated Dartboard Experiment – Left and Right Alternative

Authors:

Parker, Smith, parker.smith@psycho.uni-tuebingen.de, University of Tuebingen

Carolin, Dudschig, carolin.dudschig@uni-tuebingen.de, University of Tuebingen

Barbara, Kaup, barbara.kaup@uni-tuebingen.de, University of Tuebingen

1) Data collection: Have any data been collected for this study already?

No data has been collected beforehand.

2) Hypothesis: What's the main question being asked or hypothesis being tested in this study?

The main hypotheses investigated in this study relate to the effects of instructions on a participant's performance. Here, the task is throwing darts at a dartboard, trying to hit the center. The instructions used are either affirmatively or negatively phrased and refer to areas of the board that should or should not be avoided. These areas always relate to either the left or right of the dartboard. We anticipate participants will behave differently depending on the use of negative or affirmative instructions.

In this experiment, different zones of the dartboard are established. Overall, the participants are directed to hit the bullseye of the dartboard, which is located at the center (**goal zone**). Within each block of six trials, an area of the dartboard is specified as an **acceptable zone**, while another is a **to-be-avoided zone**. The zones are always either the right half ($x > 0$) or the left half ($x < 0$) of the dartboard. In affirmative trials, this is done by specifying the **acceptable zone** directly (e.g. "Your main goal is to hit the center. If you make an error, make sure the dart is in the right/left zone."). In negative trials, this is done by specifying the to-be-avoided zone (e.g. "Your main goal is to hit the center. If you make an error, make sure the dart is not in the left/right zone.").

The **first hypothesis** tests that the instructions are followed, and that throwing is impacted by the instruction. Two dependent measures will be used (a horizontal measure and a count-based measure; for a detailed description of the measures see below). We will only look at the affirmative conditions for this hypothesis:

1. H_0 : The difference of means between the distribution of darts will not be significantly different when the right half of the board is an acceptable zone compared to when the left half of the board is an acceptable zone, considering they are instructed to aim for the center. Likewise, the count of darts in the acceptable zone will equal the count of darts in the to-be-avoided zone.

H_A : The difference of means between the distribution of darts will be significantly different when the right half of the board is an acceptable zone compared to when the left half of the board is an acceptable zone, considering they are instructed to aim for the center. Likewise, the count of darts in the acceptable zone will be larger than the count of darts in the to-be-avoided zone.

The **second hypothesis** investigates whether negation results in overall stronger or more errors. For this hypothesis, our dependent measures will be the distance of the dart to the center of the board as well as the number of darts outside of the center circle.

H_0 : Blocks with negative instructions result in the same amount and degree of errors as blocks with affirmative instructions.

H_A : Blocks with negative instructions result in overall more and larger errors than blocks with affirmative instructions.

The **third hypothesis** investigates the idea of ironic negation. For this hypothesis, our dependent measures will again be the horizontal measure and a count-based measure:

H_0 : Blocks with negative instructions do not result in darts closer to/located within the to-be-avoided zone than blocks with affirmative instructions (when the acceptable avoided zones are conceptually the same, e.g., right vs. not left).

H_A : Blocks with negative instructions result in horizontal measures biased more strongly towards the to-be-avoided zone than blocks with affirmative instructions (when the acceptable/avoided zones are conceptually the same, e.g., right vs. not left). Likewise, blocks with negative instructions will result in more darts located in the to-be-avoided zone than blocks with affirmative instructions. In other words, negative instructions result in ironic errors, with participants violating the rules more often than with affirmative instructions.

3) Dependent variable: Describe the key dependent variable(s) specifying how they will be measured.

The (x,y) coordinates of the darts will be recorded. The dartboard will be treated as a unit circle with radius 1 centered at the point (0,0). Each throw will be recorded on the dartboard as a point, in principle allowing us to record both the central tendency and the spread of the darts per condition. The core dependent variables are the horizontal measure and the distance to the center.

Distance to center: The length of the line connecting the location of the dart to the center point (0,0).

Horizontal measure: The horizontal distance (x) from the central vertical axis of the dartboard to a thrown dart. This measure will allow us to measure the size of the errors in specifically the horizontal direction. For this, we will continue to treat the dartboard as a unit circle with a radius of 1 with its center as (0,0).

Count-based measure: Count of the darts in the respective zones of interest.

4) Conditions: How many and which conditions will participants be assigned to?

The experiment is a within-subject design where participants are subjected to four possible conditions (whereby right vs. left is a counterbalancing condition):

1. Affirmative-Right: Participants will be told, “Your main goal is to hit the center. If you make an error, make sure the dart is in the right zone.”
2. Affirmative-Left: Participants will be told, “Your main goal is to hit the center. If you make an error, make sure the dart is in the left zone.”
3. Negative-Right: Participants will be told “Your main goal is to hit the center. If you make an error, make sure the dart is not in the left zone.”
4. Negative-Left: Participants will be told “Your main goal is to hit the center. If you make an error, make sure the dart is not in the right zone.”

5) Analyses: Specify exactly which analyses you will conduct to examine the main question/hypothesis.

Hypothesis 1:

Horizontal measure: A one-sided, paired sample t-test will be employed with the conditions Affirmative-Right vs. Affirmative-Left, using positive vs. negative horizontal measure values depending on whether the right or the left is to be aimed for.

Count-based measure: A chi-square test will be conducted with the conditions Affirmative-Right vs. Affirmative-Right.

Hypothesis 2:

Distance-to-the-center: A one-sided paired sample t-test will be employed with the conditions of Affirmative vs. Negative for determining differences in the degrees of error.

Count-based measure: A chi-square test will be conducted with the conditions Affirmative vs. Negative to determine differences in the quantity of errors.

Hypothesis 3:

Horizontal measure: A one-sided paired sample t-test will be employed with the conditions Affirmative vs. Negative, using positive vs. negative horizontal measure values depending on whether the right or the left is the to-be-avoided zones.

Count-based measure: A chi-square test will be conducted with the conditions Affirmative vs. Negative.

6) Outliers and Exclusions: Describe exactly how outliers will be defined and handled, and your precise rule(s) for excluding observations.

Trials in which the participant fails to hit the board will be repeated.

7) Sample Size: How many observations will be collected or what will determine sample size?

A minimum effect size of interest was selected. The sample size was estimated based on the minimum effect size of interest for Hypothesis 3. The minimum effect size of interest was determined to be a difference between conditions of around 0.075 units (3 centimeters) with an overall standard deviation of 0.15 units (6 centimeters). A power analysis utilizing a paired sample t-test on the horizontal measure was run, with the results showing that to obtain a desired power of more than 0.80, 65 participants are required.

8) Other: Anything else you would like to pre-register?

Additional measures: For supplementary analyses, we calculate a measure combining error in the horizontal and vertical dimensions. This measure will be weighted towards the horizontal dimension due to our instructions focusing on the right and left areas of the board.

9) Name: Give a title for this pre-registration

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10) Type of study

- Experiment

11) Data source

- University lab